

Crossref Similarity Check Powered by iThenticate

Eko Wahyu Nur Sofianto
RJI Pengurus Daerah Kalimantan Selatan

Nama : Eko Wahyu Nur Sofianto
ORCID ID : [0000-0002-2607-5567](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2607-5567)
Scopus ID: 57211919231

Editorin Chief Tarbiyah: Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan (Sinta 4)
Tutor Relawan Jurnal Indonesia Provinsi Kalimantan Selatan
(Ketua Divisi Akreditasi dan Indeksasi)

Email: ekowahyu@relawanjurnal.id ekowahyu@uin-antasari.ac.id

Blogger [ekowahyu](https://www.blogger.com/ekowahyu)

Phone: 085736023858

- ▶ Crossref Similarity Check Powered by iThenticate merupakan fasilitas yang diberikan kepada publisher yang berlangganan doi
- ▶ iThenticate juga bagian dari alat similarity seperti Turnitin
- ▶ Proses berlangganan tidak sama dengan Turnitin tetapi menggunakan proses pengajuan pada crossref dengan syarat pdf yang telah dideposit minimal 90%

2. Masukkan member name dan member id

How to participate

If you're a Crossref member and have full-text URLs for Similarity Check in the metadata for at least 90% of your content, then you're eligible to join the service.

If you aren't yet a member, then you can [apply to join](#) here. You can find [more information](#) on how to include these full-text URLs in your new registrations or add them to content that you've previously registered on our support site.

You can check if you've done this properly using the widget below - just type your account name in the box below, select the correct one from the list, and your result will be automatically calculated. Don't worry, you don't need to know your Member ID.

If you do meet the obligations, the widget will link you to a form where you can apply for Similarity Check and click to accept the [service terms](#). If you don't meet the obligations, the widget will provide a CSV to download which shows all your DOIs that don't have the links. It will also provide instructions for how to add the missing full-text URLs.

Member Name

Member ID

3. Setelah memasukkan nama dan id doi, klik check

click to accept the service terms. if you don't meet the threshold, the widget will provide a .csv file to download which shows all your DOIs that don't have Similarity Check full-text URLs. It will also provide instructions for how to add the missing full-text URLs.

Member Name

[Yayasan Marwah Madani Riau \(ID:34280\)](#)

Member ID

Results for Yayasan Marwah Madani Riau (ID:34280)

35/35 = 100.00%

Good news - you're eligible to apply for our Similarity Check service.

You can now [apply here](#) and accept the service terms.

Once we receive your application, we'll work with the team at Turnitin to confirm that they can access your

By using our website you are consenting to our use of cookies in accordance with our Privacy Policy [OK](#)

Langkah-langkah

4. Setelah keluar hasil check pdf yang telah diupload pada deposit sampai pada minimal 90% maka melanjutkan ke proses pengisian identitas selanjutnya.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `crossref.org/_apply/simcheck/`. The page title is "Similarity Check Application". A progress bar at the top indicates three steps: "Your details" (highlighted in blue), "Service contacts", and "Sponsorship & terms". Below the progress bar, a red note states: "Mandatory fields are marked with an *". The main section is titled "About you" and contains the following form fields:

1) What is your name?*

First name

Last name

Email address

Langkah-langkah

5. Bila belum sampai pada minimal 90% upload pdf, maka klik csv dan penuhi berapa kekurangan upload pdf dan isikan kolom csv

Member Name

Member ID

Results for Sunan Gunung Djati State Islamic
University of Bandung (ID:6205)

1325/1814 = 73.04%

[Generate CSV](#)

We're sorry, but you are not eligible to register for our Similarity Check service just yet.

To be eligible you need to register full-text urls for Similarity Check pointing to the full text article for more than 90% of your content. You can find out how to add these full-text urls for Similarity Check to your existing content [here](<https://support.crossref.org/hc/en-us/articles/215774943-Depositing-full-text-URLs-for-Similarity-Check#supplemental>). To see exactly which content items are missing the full text article, simply click the "Generate CSV" button above. Please note, this CSV can only show the first 10k content items. If you have more than 10k content items missing DOIs, please contact us on [support@crossref.org] (<mailto:support@crossref.org>).

Langkah-langkah

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Excel interface with the following data in columns A and B:

	A	B
1	DOI	<item crawler="iParadigms">
2	10.15575/isin.v1i1.1	NULL
3	10.15575/isin.v1i1.5	NULL
4	10.15575/isin.v1i1.2	NULL
5	10.15575/isin.v1i1.4	NULL
6	10.15575/isin.v1i1.6	NULL
7	10.15575/isin.v1i1.42	NULL
8	10.15575/isin.v1i1.43	NULL
9	10.15575/isin.v1i1.9	NULL
10	10.15575/isin.v1i1.10	NULL
11		

DOI	<item crawler="iParadigms">
10.15575/isin.v1i1.1	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/viewFile/1/pdf_1
10.15575/isin.v1i1.5	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/5/pdf_12
10.15575/isin.v1i1.2	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/2/pdf_4
10.15575/isin.v1i1.4	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/2/pdf_4
10.15575/isin.v1i1.6	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/2/pdf_4
10.15575/isin.v1i1.42	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/42/pdf_18
10.15575/isin.v1i1.43	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/43/pdf_16
10.15575/isin.v1i1.9	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/9/pdf_15
10.15575/isin.v1i1.10	http://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/isin/article/view/9/pdf_15

Langkah-langkah

6. Bila sudah diisi csv maka upload pada deposit crosreff
<http://www.crossref.org/webDeposit>

The image shows a browser window displaying the Crossref webDeposit form. The browser address bar shows [crossref.org/webDeposit/](http://www.crossref.org/webDeposit/). The page title is "webDeposit form".

At the top, there are radio buttons for "Select Data Type":
 Journal Book Conference Proceedings Report Dissertation Crossmark Policy page
 NLM File **BETA** Supplemental-Metadata Upload **BETA**

The main section is titled "Step 2: Identify the Journal". It contains a "Journal information" section with the following fields:
Title+
Abbr+
Journal DOI+
Journal URL
Print ISSN+ Elect ISSN+ Journal DOI and/or ISSN required
Volume Issue
Issue DOI
Issue URL

Below this is the "Publication dates" section with a note: "note: use numerical values (YYYY, MM, DD)".
Type: print
*Year Month: Day:
Type: online
*Year Month: Day:
* a minimum of one publication year is required
+ complete Title, Abbr., Journal DOI/URL and/or ISSN fields for title-level Journal deposit

At the bottom of the form are two buttons: "Submit Journal/Issue DOI" and "Add Articles".

Overlaid on the right side of the browser window is a "Crossref Login" modal window. It features the Crossref logo, a "Username" field, a "Password" field with a toggle icon, a "LOGIN" button, and a link for "FORGOTTEN YOUR PASSWORD?".

Langkah-langkah

6. Setelah itu cek kembali pada url

<https://www.crossref.org/services/similarity-check/>

7. Pada bagian sponsor bila menggunakan sponsor RJI maka pilih yes dengan sponsor Relawan Jurnal Indonesia bila tidak (instansi langsung berlangganan bisa langsung diisi No)

The screenshot shows a web browser window at the URL `crossref.org/_apply/simcheck/`. The page has three navigation tabs: "Your details", "Service contacts", and "Sponsorship & terms", with the last one being active. A dropdown menu is open, displaying a list of sponsor options. The option "Yes - Relawan Jurnal Indonesia" is highlighted in blue. Below the list, there is a radio button for "No - I am a direct member" and a "Next" button with a right-pointing arrow.

- Yes - Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- Yes - Publishing House for Science and Technology, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology
- Yes - Publishing House Helvetica
- Yes - CTAnalytics India
- Yes - Relawan Jurnal Indonesia**
- Yes - Research and Innovation Center LLC
- Yes - Research and Social Study Institute (ReSSI)
- Yes - Research Support Center
- Yes - Sabinet Online Ltd
- Yes - Scientificomm LLC
- Yes - Scientific Research Solution Pvt. Ltd
- Yes - Sequence Research & Development Private Limited
- Yes - Shapovalov Scientific Publishing OU
- Yes - Sim-Chi Scientific Press Pte. Ltd (Singapore)
- Yes - Stichting OpenAccess
- Yes - Technology Research and Innovation Markaz (SMC-Private) Limited
- Yes - TechWheels.net
- Yes - Terceiro Andar International
- Yes - Thoth Open Metadata
- Yes - Tubitak Ulakbim DergiPark

No - I am a direct member

Next >

☰ Gmail

🔍 Search mail

✍ Compose

📁 Inbox 35

★ Starred

🕒 Snoozed

▶ Sent

📄 Drafts

∨ More

Labels +

2 of 269 < >

Thanks for your application for the Similarity Check service.

I've confirmed that you have full text Similarity Check URLs registered for over 90% of your content with Crossref, and the team at Turnitin will now check that they can successfully index your content and add it to the iThenticate database.

If Turnitin is unable to index your content, they will get in contact with the technical contact provided on your application form directly, within approximately 2 working days. If there are problems it's often because the content is behind access control and you haven't yet safelisted the Turnitin IP address. You won't be able to start using Similarity Check until Turnitin can index your content.

If they can index your content, Turnitin will send login details to the editorial contact provided on your application within 4-6 working days. The email will come from noreply@ithenticate.com and will have the subject line "Account Created". (Do ask your editorial contact to add noreply@ithenticate.com into the contacts, safelist or safe senders list in their email system to ensure that they definitely receive the email).

Don't forget, you'll need to ensure that you continue to have Similarity Check URLs for over 90% of your content. Do make sure you include Similarity Check URLs in the metadata of any new DOIs that you register with us and incorporate it into your processes. If you fall below 90% you risk losing access to the service. Your Sponsoring Organization should be able to help you continue to meet the obligations.

Also, please note, Similarity Check should only be used to check work that has been submitted for publication. If your organization is a University and you also wish to check student work, you will need to speak to Turnitin directly about a separate subscription for this.

Warm regards,
Kathleen

Conclusion

- 1. iThenticate diberikan bagi semua jurnal yang berlangganan doi*
- 2. iThenticate diaktifkan dengan mengisi batas minimum upload pdf pada crossref*
- 2. Konfirmasi diberikan setelah pengisian form request iThenticate*
- 3. Setelah mendapatkan akun login ada ketentuan bahwa penggunaan iThenticate pada cek similarity selain artikel yang digunakan pada jurnal misalnya skripsi, buku dll. Apabila dilanggar maka diblokir akun.*
- 4. Gratis 100 artikel setelah itu biaya dibenbankan bersamaan dengan doi tahunan*

“

<https://forum.relawanjournal.id/viewtopic.php?f=22&t=743>

”

TERIMA KASIH

Any questions?

You can find me at ekowahyu@relawanjurnal.id